

Transference Number of Cations

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Membrane potential has been used for determining the transference number^{1,2} of cations. In the present work modified Kittelberger's equation for transference number of cations

$$t_+ = \left[\frac{Z_+ \cdot Z_-}{Z_- + Z_+} \right] \left[RT \ln \frac{f_1 \cdot C_1}{f_2 \cdot C_2} + \frac{Z_+}{Z_+ \cdot Z_-} \right]$$

has been applied on cobalt ferrocyanide membrane³. For the calculation of transference number of cations various values of membrane potential were substituted in the equation and the effects of dilution on membrane potential and mobilities of anions were also studied. The electrolytes viz., salts of potassium, sodium and ammonium have been used in the present work.

Michaelis⁴ method has been used to determine the potential values. The electrolytes of the following concentrations have been used.

- (1) 0.2 and 0.02M; (2) 0.133 and 0.0133M; (3) 0.1 and 0.01M; (4) 0.04 and 0.004M; (5) 0.02 and 0.002M; (6) 0.01 and 0.001M; (7) 0.002 and 0.0002M.

TABLE I

Membrane potential of Cobalt ferrocyanide

Electrolytes	Potential (m.V.) at different concentrations						
	1.	2.	3.	4.	5.	6.	7.
KCL	10.0	14.0	16.0	17.0	18.0	23.0	29.3
KNO ₃	15.0	16.0	18.6	21.4	26.3	31.3	37.0
K ₂ SO ₄	17.2	22.7	27.0	32.2	35.4	38.3	40.9
K ₃ FeCY ₆	22.3	25.2	29.1	36.8	42.4	45.6	49.8
K ₄ FeCY ₆	24.3	27.6	31.4	40.5	44.6	47.4	51.9
NaCl	12.2	15.3	18.4	20.2	26.0	32.5	36.5
NaNO ₃	16.2	17.2	20.0	24.7	32.5	34.5	37.9
Na ₂ SO ₄	22.0	24.6	29.5	31.2	33.0	37.3	41.9
NH ₄ Cl	13.3	17.2	19.7	23.2	27.2	31.4	39.3
NH ₄ NO ₃	18.2	21.3	23.4	27.5	33.0	36.0	44.0
(NH ₄) ₂ SO ₄	25.0	28.0	30.4	35.3	38.0	42.0	49.3

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TABLE II

Transference numbers of cations

Electrolytes	Calculated transference numbers at different concentrations				
	1.	3.	5.	6.	7.
KCl	.58880	.64085	.65580	.69790	.74875
KNO ₃	.64455	.67355	.73200	.77225	.81650
K ₂ SO ₄	.54412	.66512	.75440	.78292	.79826
K ₃ FeCY ₆	.71871	.79995	.88566	.93141	.93726
K ₄ FeCY ₆	.74864	.88344	.89520	.95560	.96080
NaCl	.60855	.66230	.72545	.78015	.80985
NaNO ₃	.65140	.68260	.78580	.80040	.82255
Na ₂ SO ₄	.67672	.74106	.75532	.78240	.83132
NH ₄ Cl	.61255	.66670	.73015	.76565	.83245
NH ₄ NO ₃	.65400	.69795	.77920	.80455	.87280
(NH ₄) ₂ SO ₄	.61532	.67626	.76200	.80706	.88940

TABLE III

Mobilities of anions

Anions	True Mobilities	Calculated mobilities at different concentrations				
		1.	3.	5.	6.	7.
<i>Potassium Salts</i>						
Cl ⁻	74.6	52.02	41.76	39.08	32.25	25.00
NO ₃ ⁻	71.5	41.09	36.11	27.28	21.98	16.75
$\frac{1}{2}$ SO ₄ ²⁻	80.0	30.84	18.69	12.11	10.33	9.417
$\frac{1}{3}$ FeCY ₆ ³⁻	100.9	9.497	6.198	3.208	1.835	1.711
$\frac{1}{4}$ FeCY ₆ ⁴⁻	111.0	6.253	2.450	1.760	0.8690	0.7668
<i>Sodium Salts</i>						
Cl ⁻	74.6	32.73	25.95	19.26	14.33	11.96
NO ₃ ⁻	71.5	27.24	23.67	13.89	12.69	10.98
$\frac{1}{2}$ SO ₄ ²⁻	80.0	12.15	8.892	8.245	7.082	6.471
<i>Ammonium Salts</i>						
Cl ⁻	74.6	40.59	32.15	23.77	19.68	12.94
NO ₃ ⁻	71.5	34.02	27.82	18.23	15.63	9.412
$\frac{1}{2}$ SO ₄ ²⁻	80.0	20.09	15.39	10.04	7.681	4.000

DISCUSSION

The membrane potential of cobalt ferrocyanide decreases in the order $\text{FeCY}_6^{4-} > \text{FeCY}_6^{3-} > \text{SO}_4^{2-} > \text{NO}_3^- > \text{Cl}^-$ for potassium, sodium, and ammonium salts at different concentrations.

It is clear from the Table I that the ions are preferentially adsorbed at the surface of membrane, making it progressively more electronegative in character. At a particular stage, depending on the concentration of the electrolyte, membrane assumes charge stability and similar potential values could be realized for the process even after replacing the solution with the fresh solution or disturbing the position of the membrane. These results indicate that the membrane assumes equilibrium with the entire solution and once it has the charge stability, the geochemical effect is absent.

The membrane potential is due to the preferential adsorption on membrane surface^{5,6} is quite evident from the result obtained by us. Earlier workers also obtained the similar results while studying permeability and adsorption.

The values of transference number so obtained from the membrane potential increase slightly with the dilution, which are in accordance with earlier workers^{7,8} who have observed the same phenomenon in different systems.

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